

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Video Assisted Teaching Programme on Toilet Training of Toddlers among Parents in a Selected Rural Area at Mangalore, Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka State

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Abstract:- The current study was undertaken in a rural area of Mangalore, Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka, to assess the effectiveness of a video assisted teaching programme on toilet training of toddlers among parents. The objectives of the study were to determine the existing knowledge of parents regarding toilet training, to find the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on toilet training and to find the association between pre-test knowledge scores of parents on toilet training with selected demographic variables. Non-Probability Purposive sampling technique was used to select a sample of 40 parents from rural area. The researcher created her own toilet training knowledge questionnaire and video. The findings revealed that the pre-test knowledge level of all the parents was Moderate 60%, poor 35% and good 2%, and the post-test knowledge level very good 12.5%, good 70.5% and moderate 12.5%. The post-test knowledge score (21.78 ± 2.16) was higher than the pre-test knowledge score (14.03 ± 2.665). Paired test was used to find the effectiveness. The estimated value in knowledge (19.23, $P < 0.005$) and was greater than the table value (1.68). This demonstrated that administering the Video Assisted Program resulted in a considerable increase in knowledge. Association between pre-test knowledge with demographic variables revealed that there was significant association between the pre-existing knowledge with these demographic variables on toilet training. The findings of the study have implications in nursing practice, nursing education, nursing administration and nursing research.

Keywords:- Video assisted teaching programme, Toilet training, Parents, Toddlers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Childhood is a crucial time in a person's life; it is at this time that a person's good and bad habits are typically formed. If we educate a youngster good value, he will usually demonstrate them until the end of his life. As a result, we must begin teaching positive habits as early as childhood¹. The best time to teach excellent sanitary practises is throughout childhood. The first and most crucial hygiene practise is proper excreta disposal.

A. Need for the study

Parents play a crucial role in their children's toilet training. They have a variety of responsibilities when it comes to toilet training their child, including determining the toddler's readiness, providing a potty, establishing a regular toilet training pattern, reacting calmly and quietly if the child has an accident, and finally, being knowledgeable about the various steps of toilet training². However, studies show that they only have a rudimentary understanding of their children's potty training³.

B. Problem Statement

A study to assess the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on toilet training of toddlers among parents in a selected rural area at Mangalore, Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka state.

C. Objectives

The objectives of the study are to

- Determine the existing knowledge of parents regarding toilet training using a structured knowledge questionnaire
- Find the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on toilet training among parents using the same structured knowledge questionnaire.
- Find the association between pre-test knowledge scores of parents on toilet training with selected demographic variables.

D. Operational Definitions

- **Effectiveness:** In this study it refers to the usefulness of video assisted teaching programme on toilet training as measured by a structured knowledge questionnaire regarding toilet training.
- **Video assisted programme:** Refers to video as a medium of giving information to Parents regarding toddler's toilet training which is prepared in Kannada, the time duration is 30 minutes.
- **Toilet training:** Refers to teaching the parents of toddlers to train their children regarding the use of toilet/potty and make the parents aware about the meaning, indications, and steps of toilet training, effects of faulty toilet training practice, do's and

don'ts of toilet training and the guidelines for night time control.

- **Toddler:** Refers to the boy or girl between the age group of one to three years who are living in a rural area at Mangalore
- **Parents:** Refers to father or mother who is taking care of the toddler in a selected rural area at Mangalore and present at the time of data collection.
- **Rural area:** Refers to Indira nagar area coming under Surathkal PHC.

E. Hypothesis

- H1: The mean post-test knowledge score of parents of toddlers on toilet training will be significantly higher than the mean pre-test knowledge scores.
- H2: There will be a significant association between the pre-test knowledge score of parents of toddlers on toilet training with selected demographic variables.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The design is the structure of any scientific work. It gives direction and systematizes the research⁶. Pre-experimental, i.e., one group pre-test post-test design was adopted for the study. Here only one group was observed twice, before and after introducing the independent variable.

B. Setting of the Study

The study was conducted at Indira nagar Anganwadi which is a rural area under Surathkal PHC.

C. Population

The population selected for the study comprised of parents of toddlers staying in Indiranagar rural area at Mangalore.

D. Sample Size

In this study, number of samples comprised of 40 parents of toddlers staying in Indiranagar rural area at Mangalore.

E. Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling technique was used to select 40 samples.

F. Criteria for Sample Selection

a) Inclusion criteria

Parents of toddlers who are

- Willing to participate in the study
- Available during the time of data collection
- Able to read and write Kannada

b) Exclusion criteria

Parents of toddlers who are attended some education programme related to toilet training.

G. Description of the tool

The tool used for the study was a Structured knowledge questionnaire which is designed to collect relevant information from parents regarding their knowledge towards toilet training and to assess the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on toilet training. The tool is divided into two parts,

Part I: Demographic Performa -This is designed to elicit the demographic information from respondents consisting 10 items.

Part II: Structured Knowledge questionnaire-This is designed to elicit the knowledge of parents regarding toilet training, consisting of 30 items.

H. Score Interpretation

This questionnaire consists of 30 multiple choice questions under different areas.

Each question had four options with one correct answer and three distractors. Each correct answer carries one mark and wrong answers a score of zero, with a total of 30 marks. Overall score was categorized as follows;

0 - 12	=	Poor
13 - 18	=	Moderate
19 - 24	=	Good
25 - 30	=	Very good

I. Development of Video Assisted Teaching Programme

The investigator created a video assisted teaching programme based on a review of the literature, material preparation and organisation, video script preparation, video clip production, video editing, and video evaluation.

III. RESULTS**n=40**

Demographic variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
<25	7	17.5
26-30	16	40
31-35	11	27.5
≥36	6	15
Education		
Primary	5	12.5
Upper primary	7	17.5
High School	21	52.5
Diploma/ PUC	7	17.5
Graduate	0	0
Professional	0	0

Table 1: Distribution of subjects based on age and education

Table 1 shows that the majority of the participants (40 percent) are between the ages of 26 and 30. The majority of participants' parents (52.5%) had completed high school.

n=40

Demographic variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	4	10
Female	36	90
Religion		
Hindu	32	80
Christian	0	0
Muslim	8	20
Others	0	0
Number of Children		
1	12	30
2	23	57.5
≥3	5	12.5

Table 2: Distribution of subjects based on gender, religion and number of children

Table 2 shows that females made up the majority of the samples (90 percent). The majority of the respondents (80%) are Hindus, while 20% are Muslims. Most of them (57.5%) had two children, with 67.5 percent of them having a toddler as their second child.

n=40

Demographic variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Occupation of the Parent		
Unemployed	2	5
House wife	31	77.5
Self-employed(business)	2	5
Professional	3	7.5
Any other	2	5
Type of Family		
Nuclear	3	7.5
Joint	27	67.5
Extended	10	25
Any other	0	0
Family Income		
≤4000	17	42.5
4001-6000	15	37.5
6001-10000	6	15
≥10001	2	5

Table 3: Distribution of subjects based on occupation, type of family and family income

Housewives account for the biggest percentage (77.5%) in the table above. The majority of them (67.5%) live in joint families. The majority of the participants' monthly income (37.5%) is in the range of 4001-6000.

Table 4: Distribution of subjects based on their previous information about toilet training and source of information

n=40

Demographic variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Information received		
Yes	40	100
No	0	0
Source of Information		
Elders relatives or friends	16	40
Television	7	17.5
Radio	0	0
Newspaper, Book or Magazine	3	7.5
Day care provider	14	35
Any other	0	0

According to the table above, all of the participants received toilet training information, with 40% of them receiving it from elders, relatives or friends.

Fig. 1: Cylinder diagram showing the distribution of parents according to the level of knowledge

According to the data in the graph above, majority (60%) of the parents had moderate knowledge, 35% had poor knowledge and five percentage had good knowledge. None of them had very good knowledge.

Areas	No. of items	Knowledge score								
		Pre-test(A)		Post-test(B)			Effectiveness(B-A)			
		Mean	SD	Mean %	Mean	SD	Mean %	Mean	SD (±)	Mean %
Area I	10	5.70	2.233	57	8.18	1.412	81.75	2.48	2.30	24.75
Area II	14	5.80	1.324	41.43	9.20	1.181	65.71	3.40	1.39	24.29
Area III	3	1.25	0.588	41.67	2.10	0.709	70	0.85	0.66	28.33
Area IV	3	1.28	0.716	42.50	2.30	0.516	76.67	1.03	0.86	34.17
Total	30	14.03	2.665	46.75	21.78	2.616	72.58	7.75	2.55	25.83

Table 5: Mean, SD, Mean difference of pre test and post test

Table 5 reveals that following the administration of the Video assisted teaching programme, the total mean knowledge score grew by 25.83 percent with a mean ±SD of 7.75±2.55

Level of Knowledge	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean	Mean Difference	t-test
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage			
Poor	14	35	0	0			
Moderate	24	60	5	12.5	21.78	7.75	19.23*
Good	2	5	30	75			
Very good	0	0	5	12.5			

Table 6: Comparison of level of knowledge and effectiveness in pre-test with post-test and effectiveness of the study

p < 0.05

* = Significant

The mean post-test score was much higher than the average pre-test score, according to the data. At the 0.05 level of significance, the estimated 't' value (19.23, P0.05) in the knowledge component was bigger than the table value (1.83). As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected and the research hypothesis was accepted, implying that the increase in knowledge was not accidental. Hence it is concluded that there is very highly significant gain in knowledge of parents on toilet training.

Fig. 2: Ogive of the pre-test and post-test knowledge scores of parents regarding toilet training

The data presented in the Ogives shows significant difference between the pre-test and post test scores. The knowledge pre-test median was 13.50 whereas the post-test median score was 21.50. It shows a difference of nine in knowledge. The Ogives plotted shows that the first quartile score of post-tests is higher than third quartile score of pre-tests. This indicates that there is a significant increase in the knowledge of parents regarding toilet training

N = 40

Demographic variable	Knowledge			
	χ^2	df	p-value	Inference
Age	0.102	1	0.749	NS
Education	1.071	1	0.301	NS
Gender	0	1	1	NS
Religion	0	1	1	NS
No: of children	1.071	1	0.301	NS
Birth order of the toddler	1.20	1	0.273	NS
Occupation	0	1	1	NS
Type of family	0	1	1	NS
Monthly income	0.156	1	0.693	NS
Any previous information on toilet training	0	1	-	NS
Source of information	5.104	1	0.024	S

Table 7: Association between pre-test knowledge with demographic variables

Table value= 3.84, df=1 S = Significant; NS=Not significant

Table 7 shows that at the 0.05 level of significance, the calculated chi-Square value of source of information (5.014) is greater than that of table value (3.84), rejecting the null hypothesis and concluding that there was a significant association between pre-existing knowledge and these demographic variables on toilet training.

IV. CONCLUSION

The post-test knowledge score (21.782.16) was greater than the pre-test knowledge score (14.032.665), according to the findings of this study. The effectiveness was determined using a paired 't' test. The estimated value in knowledge (19.23, $P < 0.005$) was higher than the table value (1.68). This demonstrated that administering the Video Assisted Program resulted in a considerable increase in knowledge. Association between pre-test knowledge with demographic variables revealed that there was significant association between the pre-existing knowledge with these demographic variables on toilet training.

A. NURSING IMPLICATIONS:

The findings of the study have implications on nursing practice, nursing education, nursing administration and nursing research.

B. RECOMMENDATIONS

- This study can be replicated in urban areas.
- In both rural and urban regions, a comparative study can be undertaken to examine the knowledge of parents of toddlers regarding toilet training.
- In order to generalise the findings, a large-scale investigation is required.
- The parents' toilet-training practises can also be included in this research.
- Because health workers are in charge of PHC, this study can be conducted on them.

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